

SOP Title	Taking environmental swab samples for TRACS-Liverpool study		
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Introduction

The TRACS-Liverpool (Tracking AMR Across Care Settings in Liverpool) study aims to track transmission of extended-spectrum beta lactamase and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (ESBL-E/CPE) in hospitals and care homes in Liverpool. We will do this by recruiting care homes and hospital patients and collecting stool and associated environmental samples over a period of months. By testing these samples for ESBL-E/CPE organisms and using gene sequencing techniques to track bacteria we hope to identify where transmission of resistant bacteria is happening. We then aim to combine this information with routine data on antibiotic usage and patterns of care and will work with the hospital flow teams and participating care homes to co-design and pilot interventions to block transmission and, ultimately, reduce the number of drug-resistant infections.

1. Purpose

This method is applicable to the taking of environmental swabs associated with the TRACS-Liverpool Study.

2. Responsibilities

- Collection team
 - Correct labelling of collection tubes.
 - Recording swab number and location information on environmental sample collection paperwork
- Laboratory staff
 - Receiving samples from collection team and complete sample collection log.
 - Transferring information from sample collection paperwork to current TRACS environmental spreadsheet

3. Definitions and Abbreviations

TRACS	Tracking AMR Across Care Settings
LSTM	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
ESBL-E	Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase-producing Enterobacterales

4. Related Documents

TRACS_SOP_004	Environmental swab processing
TRACS_SOP_002	Staff hand sampling
Risk Assessment for Work with Hazardous Biological Agent_TRACS	Risk assessment
TRACS environmental spreadsheet	

5. Risk Assessment

<i>Hazard (Cause and Consequence)</i>	<i>Affected Groups</i>	<i>Existing controls (e.g., PPE...)</i>
<i>Biological Hazards</i>		
Environmental swabs: potential infection	Collection team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear PPE (gloves) when handling swabs • No sleeves • For spills on site, refer to local guidance. • For spills on transport to the laboratory refer to section 7.3
<i>Chemical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A
<i>Physical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A

6. Sample Collection/Workflow

6.1 Study outline

Collect environmental swabs from areas outlined in TRACS study protocol and deliver to LSTM lab for processing.

6.2 Recording swab data

Use environmental sample collection paperwork to record all data during sample collection. Information on paperwork will be transferred to current 'TRACS environmental spreadsheet' on the LSTM shared drive.

7. Procedure

7.1 Equipment and Reagents

7.1.1 Consumables required

Materials	Company/Code
Gloves	Starlabs/SG-C-(size: S, M, L)
Polystyrene Swab Dacron Tip in Tube	TS/19-G
Sterile plastic template (10x10cm)	SLS/TS15-T
Azo wipes	Appleton Woods/GC322
Clear storage bags	Fisher/BAJ-340-091N
Transport box	Sarstedt/95.1720
Timer	Fisher/ 13023023
15mL falcons with sterile PBS	Fisher/352096/10010023

7.2 Environmental sample collection

1. Use the numbers on the printed map to locate the corresponding site number listed on the sample collection paperwork.
2. Record the sample data on the sample collection paperwork. This includes location information, swab number, date + time and PBS number.
3. Remove the swab from the tube and dip into a tube containing sterile PBS to moisten. Ensure that the swab does not contact surfaces or your hand before touching the PBS. If it does, discard the swab and start the process again with a new swab. Replace the lid of the PBS immediately after using.
4. Locations should be swabbed for 20 seconds, rotating the swab continuously. Follow the guidance below for each type of sampling location:

- **Toilets:** Swab around the seat then down into the bowl, without touching the water. If there is cleaning product in the toilet, do not swab areas with the product. If the toilet is soiled, record this on the paperwork.
- **Sinks:** Start swabbing at the tap handles, then to the tap outlet, basin, and finally the drain. If necessary, run the tap to rinse away any debris lifted into the basin from the drain.
- **Shower heads:** Swab all around the shower head and handle.
- **Shower drains:** Swab the surface of the drain, then swab inside the sides of the drain, aiming to sample as much area as possible.
- **Door handles:** Swab as much area on the door handle (push plate) as possible during the time. When at double doors, swab both handles.
- **Flat surfaces:** Place the sterile plastic template over the area to be swabbed. Carefully swab the area for a period of 20 seconds swabbing in all directions as shown in the figure below:

Once swabbing has been completed, clean the template with an azo wipe and reuse for following sites that day. Discard the template after each round of swabbing.

- **Other (e.g keyboards, telephones):** Swab all over the surface, rotating the swab.
5. Return the swab to the transport tube, ensuring that it does not contact the outside of the tube or other surfaces before entering. If this happens, mark the swab to be discarded and re-sample with a new swab. Place used swabs into a transport box separate from the unused swabs.
 6. After swabbing door handles, flat surfaces and 'other' sites, clean the swabbed area using an azo wipe to remove any remaining PBS that may have transferred from the swab. Discard the wipes into a clear storage bag. Wipes can then be discarded into a yellow clinical waste bag on site or when taken back to the lab.
 7. Continue until all sampling locations have been swabbed. Change to a new tube of sterile PBS every 5 samples and mark which number of PBS has been used on the sample sheet.
 8. Transport samples to the LSTM laboratory and store at 4°C until processing according to TRACS_SOP_004

7.3 Spill procedure

In the unlikely event of a spill occurring, follow local guidelines for how to clean up. If samples are spilt/opened during transport to the laboratory, cross-contamination may have occurred. Any open swab tubes will be transferred to a class II microbiological safety cabinet and dealt with according to laboratory SOPs. The details will be recorded, and a decision made by a senior member of the lab team whether to process the samples or discard them.

8. Review History

18.07.2023: minor changes to swabbing procedure (new PBS every 5 samples).

06.09.2023: Changes made to reflect sample recording. Detail added to swabbing instructions to give specific instructions for each type of sampling location.

22.02.24: Changes made to clarify where collection team should record swabbing information. Changes also made to add more detail about when to use azo wipes and where to dispose of them afterwards.